

Studies on Thiazolidinones. Part-XIX¹. Synthesis of Thiazolidinones and their Derivatives from 2-Hydrazinobenzothiazole

B. K. GARNAIK, N. MISHRA, M. SEN and A. NAYAK*

P. G. Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Jyoti Vihar, Burla-768 019

Manuscript received 18 August 1989, revised 1 December 1989, accepted 6 December 1989

The synthesis of 2-(benzothiazolylamino-2')imino-4-thiazolidinone (1a), 3-phenyl-2-(benzothiazolylamino-2')-imino-4-thiazolidinone (2a) and 3-(benzothiazolylamino-2')-2-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (3a) have been made from 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole through different routes. The arylidene derivatives of the parent thiazolidinones have been prepared by reacting them with different aromatic aldehydes. The structures of the compounds have been established by the spectral and analytical data.

A large number of compounds possessing benzothiazole moiety exhibit several pharmacological activities². The industrial importance of such compounds are also numerous³. The synthesis and bactericidal activities of thiazolidinone derivatives possessing the benzothiazole moiety at 2-position through imino function have been reported from this laboratory earlier⁴. Therefore, in continuation of our work⁵ we report herein the synthesis of three series of thiazolidinone derivatives linked to a benzothiazole moiety through different functionalities. In the first and second series, it is linked to thiazolidinone ring at C-2 through an hydrazono function whereas in the third one it is linked to the same position through an amino group.

The 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles (prepared using standard procedures⁶) gave 4-(benzothiazolyl-2')-thiosemicarbazide and 4-(benzothiazolyl-2')-1-phenylthiosemicarbazide after reaction with potassium thiocyanate and phenylisothiocyanate respectively. These compounds underwent condensation with monochloroacetic acid to give 2-(benzothiazolyl-2')-hydrazonoyl-4-thiazolidinone (1a) and 2-(benzothiazolyl-2')-hydrazonoyl-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (2a). The hydrazino-benzothiazole also gave the hydrazone with benzaldehydes, which underwent cyclocondensation with mercaptoacetic acid to generate 3-(benzothiazolyl-2')-amino-2-phenyl-4-thiazolidinones (3a). These thiazolidinones gave arylidene compounds after reaction with aromatic aldehydes in acetic acid. The thiazolidinone (2a) gave 3-phenyl-2,4-thiazolidinone after hydrolysis with alcoholic HCl along with (benzothiazolyl-2)-hydrazine confirming its structure.

The ir spectra of 1a and 2a showed carbonyl absorption at 1740 and 1730 cm⁻¹ respectively, whereas the benzylidene derivatives (1b and 2b) of both the compounds showed the carbonyl absorption at 1680 cm⁻¹. Besides these, weak peaks at

a; X=2H, b; X=C₆H₅-CH=, c; X=p-OCH₃-C₆H₄-OH=, d; X=p-Cl-C₆H₄-CH=

2900–2950 cm⁻¹ (CH₂) were absent in their benzylidene derivatives confirming the disappearance of methylene group.

Experimental

All melting points were determined in open capillaries in sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

2-Hydrazinobenzothiazole were prepared using standard procedures⁶, m.p. 190° (lit. 191°).

1-(Benzothiazolyl-2')thiosemicarbazide: A mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1.65 g, 10 mmol) and potassium thiocyanate (1.94 g, 20 mmol) in concentrated HCl (10 ml) and water (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. After cooling, the resulting colourless solid was dried and crystallised from ethanol as white needles, m.p. 141° (Found: S, 28.20. $C_8H_8N_4S_2$ requires: S, 28.57%).

1-Benzothiazolyl-2'-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide: A solution of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1.65 g, 10 mmol) in minimum amount of alcohol was treated with phenylisothiocyanate (1.35 g, 10 mmol) dropwise with stirring. The reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 0.5 h. After cooling, the resulting solid was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 179° (Found: S, 21.20. $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S_2$ requires: S, 21.33%).

2-(Benzothiazolyl-2')hydrazono-4-thiazolidinone (1a): A mixture of 1-(benzothiazolyl-2')thiosemicarbazide (2.02 g), monochloroacetic acid (0.95 g) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.6 g) in absolute ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed slowly for 3 h. The solvent was then evaporated, cooled and poured into crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed with hot water and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 158° (Found: S, 24.21. $C_{10}H_8N_4OS_2$ requires: S, 24.25%); ν_{max} 3 300br (NH), 2 900 (CH_2) and 1 740 cm^{-1} (C=O).

2-(Benzothiazolyl-2')hyrazono-3-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (2a) was prepared from 1-(benzothiazolyl-2')-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and monochloroacetic acid in equivalent quantities following the above procedure, m.p. 166° (Found: S, 18.80. $C_{16}H_{12}N_4OS_2$ requires: S, 18.82%); ν_{max} 3 400br (NH), 2 950 (CH_2) and 1 730 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Benzothiazolyl-2-benzaldehyde hydrazone: A solution of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1.65 g) and benzaldehyde (1 ml) in ethanol (20 ml) was treated with piperidine (2 drops) and refluxed on water-bath for 4 h. After cooling, the resulting yellow solid was dried and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 218° (Found: S, 12.11. $C_{14}H_{11}N_3S$ requires: S, 12.64%).

3-(Benzothiazolyl-2')amino-2-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (3a): Mercaptoacetic acid (1.5 g) added dropwise to a well-stirred solution of the above hydrazone (2.6 g) in dry benzene (70 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 6 h using a water separator. The pale yellow solid that separated after cooling was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 215° (Found: S, 19.59. $C_{16}H_{13}N_3OS_2$ requires: S, 19.57%).

2-(Benzothiazolyl-2')hydrazino-5-benzylidene-4-thiazolidinone (1b): A mixture of the thiazolidinone (1a; 2.2 g), benzaldehyde (1 ml) and fused NaOAc (1 g) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. It was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting yellow solid was washed with hot water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 183° (Found: S, 18.15. $C_{17}H_{13}N_4OS_2$ requires: S, 18.18%); ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 680, 1 590, 1 240 cm^{-1} .

Similarly other compounds were prepared from different thiazolidinones and aldehydes by following the above procedure: 1c, m.p. 142° (Found: S, 16.68. $C_{18}H_{14}N_4S_2O_2$ requires: S, 16.75%), ν_{max} 3 300–3 250 and 1 620 cm^{-1} ; 1d, m.p. 165° (Found: S, 15.32. $C_{17}H_{11}N_4S_2OCl$ requires: S, 16.55%); 2b, m.p. 122° (Found: S, 14.70. $C_{17}H_{16}N_4S_2O$ requires: S, 14.95%), ν_{max} 3 350–3 250 and 1 670 cm^{-1} ; 2c, m.p. 114° (Found: S, 13.90. $C_{24}H_{18}N_4S_2O_2$ requires: S, 13.97%); 2d, m.p. 183° (Found: S, 13.51. $C_{23}H_{15}N_4S_2OCl$ requires: S, 13.83%); 3b, m.p. 210° (Found: S, 18.20. $C_{25}H_{18}N_3S_2O$ requires: S, 15.45%) ν_{max} 3 350–3 200 and 1 690 cm^{-1} ; 3c; m.p. 170° (Found: S, 14.40. $C_{24}H_{18}N_3S_2O_2$ requires: S, 14.41%); 3d, m.p. 205° (Found: S, 16.25. $C_{23}H_{15}N_3S_2OCl$ requires: S, 14.26%).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (B.K.G.) is thankful to the Department of Environment and Forest and two of them (N.M., M.S.) are thankful to Department of Science and Technology, Government of India for financial assistance.

References

1. Part-XVIII, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, communicated.
2. S. N. SAWHNEY and J. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 882; M. COLONNA, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1948, 78, 462; A. K. EL SHAFI, A. M. EL SAYED and A. M. SOLMAN, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1987, 117, 385; P. N. DHAL and A. NAYAK, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1975, 37, 92.
3. N. RIICHI and Y. KAZUHIRO, *Jap. Pat.* 62 284 343/1987 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1988, 109, 201280).
4. P. N. DHAL, T. E. ACHARY and A. NAYAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 931.
5. B. K. GARNAIK and R. K. BEHERA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1988, 27, 1157.
6. L. KATZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 4007; V. R. RAO and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Experientia*, 1964, 20, 200 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1964, 60, 14496).